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NASA RDAC Report to the GHRSSST Science Team

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MODIS and VIIRS L2P

- Aqua and Terra L2P, v2019.0 reprocessings (complete July 2020)
 - https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/dataset/MODIS_T-JPL-L2P-v2019.0
 - https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/dataset/MODIS_A-JPL-L2P-v2019.0
- VIIRS L2P, v2016.1 reprocessing (complete June 2020)
 - https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/dataset/VIIRS_NPP-JPL-L2P-v2016.0
- Big improvements in cloud masking and number of cloud free pixels
- Operations nominal. Data within 3-4 hours of observation

MUR

- Software and processing system moved to new hardware/software
- Proposal for software refactoring and operationalizing underway
- Consideration of adding daytime observations. Improve high latitude coverage.
- MUR25 and SST anomaly layers in SOTO v4.5
- Basis of the MUR AWS Open Data Registry dataset

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- G1SST L4...has been retired

NASA Physical Oceanography

- MISST progress
 - Arctic Saildrone deployment distributed through the PO.DAAC
 - in direct collaboration with the Saildrone Project Team and Chelle Gentemann.
 - Initial comparisons of GHRSSST L4 products with Saildrone SSTs. Inclusive of all 4 sensor on board. Improvements planned for MUR data based on results.
 - Contributions to GHRSSST R/G TS re-architecture implementation
- 6 Peer Reviewed Publications
- CEOS COVERAGE Project
 - Completion of Phase A and Implementation of Phase B
 - Inclusive of a prototype, cloud access, and jupyter notebooks
 - SST data sets include GMPE and MUR25.
 - More details to be presented in SST-VC meeting